

“A pioneering method of Deep learning-based Text Summarization using Abstractive Approach with issues and challenges”

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Abstract:

Presenting most precise information by applying certain methods of Text summarization is very much essential without losing its essence. There is vast amount of online data increase problem arises due to large volume of Internet data in the form of research paper, journal, books, articles, magazines, business data etc. To deal with such enormous amount of online data, text summarization method using Deep learning based Abstractive approach specially Transformer based is very appropriate.

Deep learning based various methods, tools, techniques and approaches exists but among these methods, transformer T5 (Text to Text Transfer Transformer) is most appropriate to generate abstractive summary in concise and precise form. So, it is very much needed to reduce form of summary from original large amount of source document content. This research paper highlights and emphasizes on all methods, tools relevant to the text summarization using Deep learning-based methods with T5 transformer. This research paper deciphers different issues and challenges arise in abstractive text summarization.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing (NLP), Text Summarization, Extractive Summarization, Abstractive Text Summarization, Deep Learning.

1.INTRODUCTION:

In the current scenario, it is observed that, the text summarization obtaining significance due to occupancy of vast amount of web data. So it is very necessary to reduce it at great extent

with the help of some dynamic summarizer which summarizes various application such as newspaper, magazine, scientific paper, books, music, plays, film and speech, whether forecast, stock market data etc. Text summarization can

be broadly categories into two types namely Extractive text summarization and Abstractive text summarization.[1]

Extractive text summarization consists of text summarization of vital sentences to be included without any modification from source document contents while Abstractive summarization give emphasis on the meaning and structure of sentences in such a way that, it preserves the grammatical structure without changing meanings from the original document by applying various reduction and advanced language generation algorithms. So that the linguistic quality or readability of text summary can be improved. For generating such summary with abstractive method, paraphrasing and real-world knowledge was needed. This research paper discusses various abstractive text summarization and related work in abstractive text summarization for English language with different deep learning-based methods and approaches.

2. TEXT SUMMARIZATION TECHNIQUES

Different types of text summarization techniques can be broadly divided into following way, as shown below [2]:

A. Approaches Types : In this, extractive method only extracts vital phrases to generate summary without changing original text whereas in abstractive alternative words or phrases which are not from source document is used.

B. Details Types:

For lengthy document to summarize, an indicative type of summary used which provide idea of source text only. Informative type work as a substitution to source document providing concise information.

C. Content Types: The generic type of summarization comprises of summary which does not depends on topic of document instead it can be used by any type of user. The query based summarization gives summary based on query given by the user in question and answer form.

D. Based on language: In this, monolingual type of summarization system, the summary generated in single and same languages which is input languages of source document.e.g. English language. While in multilingual summarization, summary can be generated in multiple languages and having same languages for same input text and generated summary text. In Cross lingual summarization, summary can be generated in several languages.

E. Based on input document:

In this, single document and multi document type of inputs are taken into consideration for generating the summary.

Figure1:Types of Text Summarization.

3. DEEP LEARNING ABSTRACTIVE TEXT SUMMARIZATION

The Abstractive method of text summarization involves precise and concise meaning of large

document summary into short summary by including new words or phrases apart from source document content. There are mainly two approaches to abstractive text summarization methods mainly

- Traditional approach of abstractive text summarization.
- Abstractive text summarization on Neural Network.

In the traditional approach, human compiled feature can be achieved using domain specific understanding with the help of rule based method. It can be of two types mainly Structured based and Semantic based approaches.[3]

- The Structured based approach, consists of predefined structured to generate abstractive summary preserving the meaning using abstractive text summarization. Various predefined structure such as template based, tree based, based on Ontology, rule based structure etc. can be used to generate summary.
- The Semantic based approach generally comprises of semantic representation in natural language so as to generate summary in desire format. For this it used multimodal semantic model, semantic graph based and Information item-based methods by constructing model using concepts with ontology, information density identification and finally generating desire summary.

Neural network based abstractive text summarization: In this, there is no direct use of manually compiled features and rules based methods. An Encoder-Decoder architecture captures the essential information from source sequence pertaining to an abstractive

summarization job through deep learning neural network to generate target summary. In this the researcher, utilizes model to enhance summary using fine-grained semantic graphs. For this it can construct semantic graphs to reduce occurrence of internal hallucination errors using triple extraction with dependency parse job.[4]. For producing summary, using bi-directional RNN with LSTM's which can be used in encoder layer while attention model in decoder layer is utilized. Dealing with abstractive text summarization, text preprocessing, word embedding, vocabulary counting, missing word counting, the efficiency and fluency of text summary can be achieved.[5]

In summary generation, attention mechanism used in LSTM by assigning weights to vital parts from source document text to generate quality summary. The attention mechanism used to generate quality summary from large volume of text so that it can be improved. In Seq2Seq model, the pre-training process and attention mechanism can be used to fulfill the task of abstractive text summarization for comparing against datasets. BERT improves the performance and efficiency of model in NLP task and text summarization task. The model used BERT for understanding text word vectors and apply proper pre-processing on input text. Both sequence model with attention mechanism highlights and emphasizes significant words and preserve vital information in summary from source document [6]. A Long-Short Transformer based model use to capturing aspects in both local and global perspective while pointer network use with attention mechanism to improve the problem of unlabeled words and repeated words [7].

In recent years, text summarization gaining popularity since extensive amount of growth of web content can be reduced and

efficient and essential information can be retrieved easily. Various pre-trained T5, Pegasus, BART small and large model can be used to generate abstractive text summary on Xsum datasets, CNN/Daily Mail etc. Also, LSTM, pre-trained models and fine-tuned model was analyses and assess through datasets while BART-Large model gives best performance on with custom resume datasets [8].

The text summarization was used in various areas like NLP, Data mining, Information Retrieval (IR), Multimedia, Computer Science and Statistics. In traditional way, the text summarization methods identify vital words from documents by using quality structure of text summarization methods. An advanced method of text summarization implements adequate quality structure for generating precise, without any errors, accurately and reduced text content. Mostly, advance methods for text generation such as NLP techniques like Neural word embedding and deep learning techniques like RNN, LSTM was used for automatic text generation. Encoder-Decoder mechanism used for processing long articles or documents [9].

The research paper specifies deep learning model was used like BART comprises of encoder-decoder both. BERT is trained in such a way that unlabeled data for achieving state of art results. For predicting missing values several bidirectional transformer layer with merging of encoder and decoder forming BART model [10]. For generating sentences from keywords, rules based on discourse and syntactic related constraints were utilized. Also, an integrating various sentences together into single sentences, word graph was used for achieving abstractive summarization task [11].

Early approaches such as pre-deep learning consists of various non-neural approaches to automatically producing summaries capturing the essence of source text content. Rule-based method, template-based summarization, Word sense disambiguation (WSD), Sentence extraction, keyword-based summarization, Statistical Approaches, Graph based algorithms, Topic modeling, Clustering method, Hidden markov models etc was used for generation of text summaries from source documents. Now various methods of text summarization based on deep learning were used such as Sequence-to-Sequence model uses Encoder-Decoder architecture, Attention mechanism and Transformer based Architecture uses BERT, T5, Pegasus were used [12].

Methods	Description
Word Graph Methodology	The technique based onward graphs is separated into two components. The first component is sentence reduction, followed by sentence combination. This technique involves nodes that represent the information about words and their relation.
Semantic Graph Reduction Algorithm	The semantic graph-based approach builds a graph that summarizes the original content by gathering semantic information from words and assigning weights to nodes and edges [12].
Markov Clustering Algorithm	To construct summaries, the Markov Clustering Principle employs a hybrid technique. In this method, sentence ranking is accomplished by combining linguistic norms with the best fitting sentences inside a cluster to construct

	newsentences [12].
Encoder-Decoder Model	The encoder convertsthe input sentencesequence into a context vector, and the decoderconverts the processedinput intocomprehensible output [13].
Pegasus	In this approach,significant lines areeliminated from the inputtext and compiled asseparate outputs.
Summarization with Pointer Generator Networks	This method employs ahybrid approach,producing words from apredefined vocabularyand replicating words bypointing [13].
Genetic Semantic Graph based Approach	The approach generates asemetic graph from thesource text, with graphnodes representingpredicate argument structures (PASs) andgraph edges representingsemantic similarity weights [12]

Table 1 : Abstractive Text Summarization Techniques.

4. VARIOUS TOOLS/LIBRARY USED FOR ATS

The SUMMY is very useful library used to extract text summary which is either web pages written in HTML or simple plain texts files. This is open source library in python containing certain evaluation purpose package for textual summary. Various algorithms are useful to deal with text summarization such as heuristic based method provided by Luhn, LSA, heuristic method provided by Edmundson, LexRand and TextRank.

Second Python Library which is again a open source utilized for advanced NLP task is spaCy. For Natural Language understanding as well as extracting information specially large volumn of

content spaCy is designed and implemented in Python. Also for providing a concise and pre-processing large volumn of text using deep learning a wide variety of linguistic annotations provided deep insights into textual content in proper strucure of grammer.

GENSIM is very much quickest library written especially for to train vector embeddings and it is very much utilized on various platforms like Linux, platform such as Windows and OS X which specially supports python as well as Numpy. Also, the GENSIM is useful for generating prominent representtive sentences or summary by using variation of TextRank algorithm.

NLTK is use for removing stop words and frequecy based computation of every word in tokenized list and generate summary based on the frequency.[14]

5. ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN TEXT SUMMARIZATION:

The various challenges and issues arises consists of –

Human Language complication issues arises in Automatic text summarization since general public way of expressing mainly text in transcribed form. It is totally based on the sentence length since it increases in adjective, adverbs and propositions representation or description containing extraneous information while producing summary.

Anaphora problem issues also arises because of synonyms or pronouns utilized in text whenever introducing any topic. Also unclear words and specific term used to describe and discuss for hosting term itself known as Cataphora problem also arises. [15][16]

Non-textual content representation challenges arise because tables representing trades and industrial data, sports data etc in tabular manner.

Summary evaluation is again one of the challenges since believing in summary is really trustworthy or not representing original source document with sustaining its meaning. [17][18]

6. CONCLUSION:

It is immensely observed that a Summarization based on Deep Learning in recent advancement shown promise for improvement in term of accuracy and effectiveness of Text summarization systems. Various approaches used such as Transformers showing greatest assists in Deep learning models for generating high-quality textual summaries. Structured data utilization provides very promising approach incorporating structured data such as tables and charts which are helpful to improve the accuracy and informativeness of text summaries. Also an user feedback and personalization incorporates to improve the relevance and usefulness of text summaries for news articles or other types of content that are customized to human being interests. The latest advancement also becomes more promising in future of text summarization along with evolution or advancements in natural language processing(NLP) and machine learning leading to more concise, efficient, accurate and effective text summarization systems.

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